

Repairing the Future: Addressing E-Waste and Climate Change through Right to Repair Legislation

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Abstract—This paper explores the critical significance of the right to repair movement in addressing the escalating global e-waste crisis and its broader environmental and economic impacts. Drawing parallels between the emotional attachments we form with personal items, and increasing planned obsolescence of technology, the paper highlights the necessity of extending the lifespan of electronics products by implementing strict right to repair laws.

The paper examines the environmental consequences of e-waste, which significantly harms human health, contributes to pollution and increases greenhouse gas emission. It cites alarming statistics from the United Nations and other sources, illustrating the growing volume of e-waste and the insufficient recycling rates. By emphasizing the benefits of repair—both in reducing waste and mitigating climate change—the paper advocates for stronger legislation supporting the right to repair.

Additionally, the paper discusses the economic advantages of such legislation for consumers, producers, and governments. It reviews existing right to repair laws in the U.S. and recent developments in the European Union, emphasizing the need for comprehensive and enforceable repair rights to combat e-waste effectively. The paper concludes with a call for expanded legislation and greater support for repair practices to foster sustainability and enhance both environmental and economic efficiency.

Keywords— *Right to Repair, E-Waste, climate change, Repair Legislation, Greenhouse Gas Emissions, environmental*

1. INTRODUCTION

In 2015, I bought my first Samsung phone, the first edition of Samsung edge, the “Samsung Galaxy Note Edge” from a retail shop. Unfortunately, after 6 months, I dropped it, and the screen broken. I went to repair shop; they told me we couldn’t repair it because they didn’t have the necessary screen and advised me to go the Samsung store. Once there, they informed that the repair would cost me almost 75% of the original price. They also mentioned it would take a month to complete the repair. I was concerned about how I could manage without my phone for entire month and wondered if there an option to rent a temporary phone or they could arrange one for me to use until the repair was finished, like a car! Instead, they indirectly pressured me to buy a new phone, implying that this was better option.

This story highlighted two main issues related to the concept of the right to repair. First, the right to repair should allow me to fix my phone anywhere, not just with the manufacturer. Second, consider the scenario if Samsung could just the screen at a reasonable price, or if other manufacturers could produce same screen. In that case, repair shops could order it and fix the phone at suitable price with reasonable time.

For example, if you have a Toyota car and you need to change alternator, you can order the parts from Toyota and have them installed at any auto repair shop. Alternatively, you have the option to look on eBay for parts from other manufacturers and choose your preferred option. You can then order the parts and, if you have the tools and follow some instructional videos on YouTube, you can replace the parts yourself.

I am one of those people who deeply believe that inanimate have feelings and senses, and I form emotional attachments with them. In 1995, the first part of “Toy story” was released. I was nine years old at the time, and the movie resonated with me deeply. It reflected our feelings towards toys and inanimate objects. We saw how Andy, who own many toys, treated them with a large amount of love. When he gave more car and attention to Buzz Lightyear and loved him more, leaving his first, and favorite toy woody alone, we all felt sad for Woody. This emotional attachment extends beyond toys to our phones, laptops, wash machines, and other electronics devices. Just like humans, these devices sometimes break, get sick, need rest, and

some sometimes die when they suffer from irreparable damage.

Often, when your device breaks and disables after years of use, you still want to fix it, because you have formed relationship with it. I owned my Casio watch since 1995 and have repaired it multiple times, yet I still cherish it and take it with me whenever I travel. It’s relationship that deserves respect!

In the book “Repair Revolutions” by John Wackman & Elizabeth Knight, they throughfall articulate “ Almost every item people bring has meaning to them. Every item comes with story. Laughter and tears are common.” This beautifully words capture the emotional significance we attach to our belongings, reflecting the importances of the right to repair. it is not just about functionality, it’s about respecting connections we have with our cherished items.

Some may question whether we should have the right to repair simply because of our emotional attachment and cherished memories with our devices. While this may be part of the answer, a much larger issue considers attention: E-waste. This problem has awakened governments around the world. Countless devices end up in landfills, garbage, or remain unused at home because we cannot fix or modify them.

E-Waste is like a malignant disease spread all over the world. When examining the following statistics, we will recognize how it affects various aspects of our lives, not only in environmental health but in human health, economy, and environmental justice.

According to the United Nations Environment Programme, global E-waste produced annually is worth over \$62.5 billion, more than the GDP of most countries. Similarly, there is 100 times more gold in a ton of E-waste than in a ton of gold ore. The amount of e-waste is anticipated to reach 82 million tonnes by 2030.[1] The United States generated 7.18 million tons of E-waste in 2022 alone driven by higher consumption rates of electric/electronic equipment, short life cycles, and few options for repair according to the United Nations Institute for Training and Research (UNITAR), and only recycling only 17.7% of its material.[2] The value of the raw materials contained in the E-waste produced in the U.S. during 2019 was \$7.49 billion. Really

one of the effective solutions to mitigate and minimize e-waste is the right to repair. It is time to support, encourage, and legislate the right to repair thought strict laws. This paper aims to answers the following question: Why is the right to repair important to us, what are the right to repair laws? You will have to answer this question through this paper.

2. What is the right to repair

The right to repair movement advocates for extending the lifespan of products and keeping them in use for as long as possible. Generally, repair refers fixing or mending a broken or damaged item. To repair means “restore,” “rehabilitate,” “renovate,” “renew,” “reinforce,” “reconcile,” or “redeem. It is opposite of “wreck,” “worse,” or “destroy.” [3] Right to repair focuses on empowering consumers to repair their own products instead of going back to the original manufacturer for service.[4]

To illustrate, consider the right to repair in practical terms. If the screen of your cellphone breaks, the right to repair means you should have option to fix it yourself or have it repaired at repair shop, rather than being compelled to return it to the original manufacturer. Similarly, if the battery of your Apple Laptop, or I phone dies, the right to repair would allow you to replace the battery yourself or have it replaced at a third-party service center.

Apply this scenario with automobiles: if your car battery dies, you have option to various retailers like Walmart or AutoZone, specify your car models, and replace the battery yourself. This flexibility is an example of the right to repair in action. The right to repair encompasses not only the ability to fix devices but also access to spare parts at fair prices. It ensures

that repairs can be performed at any time—both during and after the warranty period—and at any location, whether through the manufacturer or an independent repair shop.

For a big picture, reflect on the number of older cars still in use. The longevity of these vehicles is often attributed to the ease with which they can be repaired. For instance, my 2001 Lexus recently required a new motor belt. The replacement cost \$120 and was completed by a mechanic in under an hour. This experience underscores the significance of the right to repair: it enables individuals to maintain and extend the life of their products efficiently and affordably.

In summary, the right to repair empowers consumers with the ability to repair and maintain their electronic devices at any time and in any location, whether through certified repair centers or independent options. It is ensuring access to spare parts and repair services as needed, thereby extending the lifespan of products and promoting sustainability.

3. Understanding the Significance of Repair: Environmental, Economic, and Practical Benefits

Before discussing the importance of the right to repair, let's consider some compelling numbers that show the potential impact of implementing such a right. E-Waste is like a malignant disease spread all over the world. When examining the following statistics, we will recognize how it affects various aspects of our lives, not only in environmental health but in human health, economy, and environmental justice. The global e-waste produced in 2022 was 62 million tonnes, just only 22% of that waste was formally recycled, leaving US \$62 billion worth of recoverable natural resources unaccounted for and increasing pollution risks to communities worldwide. The amount of e-waste is anticipated to reach 82 million tonnes by 2030.[5]

The United States generated 7.18 million tons of E-Waste and is only recycling only 17.7% of its material.[6] The value of the raw materials contained in the E-Waste produced in the U.S. during 2019 was \$7.49 billion.[7] The value of the raw materials contained in the E-Waste produced in the U.S. during 2019 was \$7.49 billion.[8]

Focusing specifically on mobile phones, which are ranking as first category of e-waste, it is staggering to note that approximately 400,00 mobile phones are disposed daily in the U.S, amounting to roughly 150 million each year.[9]

One of the main reasons of this issue is short life cycles of electronic devices, and the limited options for repair, according to the United Nations Institute for Training and Research (UNITAR). Therefore, the right to repair plays an essential role to minimizing and controlling e-waste, which has significantly impacted the environment, health, economy.

A. Reducing the Amount of e-waste

First, without the option for right to repair, there will be an increase in the amount of the e-waste, when devices cannot be repaired, their lifespan comes to an end, leading to their disposal as waste. Recognize that globally, only 22.3% of e-waste is documented to be formally collected and recycled. The remaining percentage, 77.7% total, is disposed of in landfills (or other non-dumping sites) or incinerated. As mentioned later the United States generated 7.18 million tons of E-Waste and is only recycling only 17.7% of its material. The right to repair will play a vital role in reducing this amount of e-waste. According to a

study published in Waste Advantage Magazine, the Right to Repair can reduce e-waste by up to 30%. In addition, According to The European Commission, 35 million tonnes of waste result from still-usable consumer goods being thrown away.

i. Environmental Health Impacts

E-waste has significant environmental impacts. The question here is: Where does e-waste ultimately end up, how can it be properly disposed of, and how frequently is e-waste recycled? These questions are essential to answer the main question about how to minimize and reduce E-waste. Unbeknownst to many consumers, electronics contain toxic substances, therefore they must be handled with care when no longer wanted or needed. E-waste contains several toxic additives or hazardous substances, such as mercury, brominated flame retardants (BFR), and chlorofluorocarbons (CFCs), or hydrochlorofluorocarbons (HCFCs). Recognize that globally, only 22.3% of e-waste is documented to be formally collected and recycled. The remaining percentage, 77.7% total, is disposed of in landfills (or other non-dumping sites) or incinerated. As mentioned later the United States generated 7.18 million tons of E-Waste and is only recycling only 17.7% of its material. [10] As mentioned later the United States generated 7.18 million tons of E-Waste and is only recycling only 17.7% of its material.

ii. Human Health Impacts

E-waste causes a wide range of harmful side effects. The consequences of improper E-waste disposal in landfills or other non-dumping sites pose serious threats to current public health and can pollute ecosystems for generations to come, standing in direct opposition to the goals of sustainable development. When disposed electronic waste is in a landfill or burned, toxic chemicals are released, polluting the Earth's air, soil, water, and negatively impacting human health. Contamination of the air occurs when E-waste is informally disposed by dismantling, shredding, or melting the materials, releasing dust particles or toxins (such as dioxins) into the environment causing air pollution and damage to respiratory health. Humans rely on air to breathe; when that air is filled with toxins it can affect a person's respiratory system. Also, just as those same chemicals can contaminate the air, they can also contaminate the water. The toxins from electronics enter the groundwater feeding into streams, ponds, and lakes. Humans rely on these freshwater sources and, if pollutants are ingested, they could lead to serious health problems. E-waste can affect soil by disrupting its chemical content with toxins, thus reducing the soil's strength, and decreasing its fertility and other biological activities. Crops are susceptible to absorbing these contaminants making farming unsafe and impracticable.

Specific to human and animal health, electronics contain toxic materials that cause direct damage to the human body. For example, the element Lead may get into the blood, kidneys, and nervous system. For animals in particular, "E-waste impacts some animal species more than others, which may be endangering these species and the biodiversity of certain regions that are chronically polluted.[11]

iii. Greenhouse Gas Emissions Impacts

Climate change and global warming have become common terms and words in today's discourse. The formal definition of the terms being significant changes in

global temperature, precipitation, wind patterns and other measures of climate that occur over several decades or longer.[12] Climate change is caused by the emission of greenhouse gases, mostly originating from human consumption of fossil fuels that (as of the present) still provide us with the essential conveniences of modern life: heat to warm our households, kinetic energy to transport us at speed over long distances, electricity to power our appliances, and power to dig, extract, melt, refine, and transform raw materials into the manufactured products we use every day.[13]

The relationship between E-Waste and climate change depends on the amount of potent greenhouse generated from E-Waste management. To understanding how right to repair significantly contributes to greenhouse gas emissions, according to the European Commission, 260 million tonnes of greenhouse gas emissions are generated each year, as a result of still-usable consumer goods being thrown away. The question arises here: does the process of E-Waste recycling generate greenhouse gases (GHGs) emission, in addition to the indirect emission associated with raw material extraction and manufacturing? Absolutely, yes E-Waste has a significant contribution to GHG emissions. E-Waste affects climate change through both direct and indirect impacts.

a. Direct Impacts of E-Waste on Climate Change

Directs impacts stem from two main sources. First, when electronic waste is openly incinerated, it releases harmful gases into the atmosphere, including carbon dioxide (CO₂) and methane (CH₄), both potent GHGs. Additionally, refrigerants and insulating foams from waste electronic and electrical equipment (WEEE) contain hydrochlorofluorocarbons (HCFCs) and hydrofluorocarbons (HFCs), which are potent GHGs.[14] Second, the leachate from landfill sites where e-waste is frequently deposited often contains high levels of organic matter. When this organic matter decomposes anaerobically, facilitated by microbes in the absence of oxygen, which cause to produce methane a greenhouse gas with a heat-trapping capacity 28 times greater than carbon dioxide.[15]

Therefore, landfilling e-waste constitutes a significant source of greenhouse gas emissions, establishing a direct connection between e-waste management practices and climate change.

b. Indirect Impacts of E-Waste on Climate Change

There is the impact on climate change driven by increasing demand for raw materials. The growing demand for electronic products, alongside shortened lifespans by following planned obsolescence methods employed by manufacturers, drives the increased extraction of raw metals. This extraction process, heavily reliant on the combustion of fossil fuels, is highly energy intensive.[16]

For instance, mobile phones are responsible for approximately 1% of global emission. In 2020, there were 7.7 billion mobile phone in use, with total footprint of roughly 580 million tons of CO₂e. Most of these emissions

arise from their manufactures and transport, particularly due to the precious metals and rare earths that need to be mined for smartphone's chips and motherboards. For examples, apple has carried out detailed life cycle carbon assessment of their products. They estimate emission caused by manufacturing and transporting an I phone 11 at 63 kg (138.8 lbs) CO₂. [17]

B. Economic Benefits

To undersetting the relationship between right to repair and economic benefits for consumers and governments, consider the scale of electronic consumption and waste. approximately 1.5 billion cell phones are produced annually, and more people own cell phones than have access to running water. In 2009 alone, an estimated 130 million cell phones were discarded un the U.S alone, highlighting the immense volume of e-waste generated.

i. Consumers Benefits of Expanding Right to Repair Legislation

A recent study found that the average U.S household spends around \$1500 annually on electronics.[18] The global e-waste produced in 2022 was 62 million tonnes, leaving \$62 billion recoverable natural resources unaccounted for.[19] In 2029, the value of the raw materials contained in the E-Waste produced in the U.S. during 2019 was \$7.49 billion.[20] The Right to Repair has the potential to alleviate the financial burden on consumers. The U.S Public Interest Research group (PIRG) highlighted that consumers could save up to \$40 billion annually if they could repair their devices instead of replacing them. In 2017, Americans broke around 50 million phone screens. For those who prefer to repair their screen, the average cost was around \$170, resulting around 3.4 billion for approximately 20 million repaired screens. Instead of repairing their phones, consumers who opted to buy new ones spent around \$20 billion.[21]

This economic benefit, coupled with the positive environmental impact, makes the Right to Repair movement a crucial part of the solution to the e-waste crisis. Moreover, the right to repair extend the lifecycle of electronic products, reducing the need for new product manufacturing and the associated environmental and economic cost. Empowering consumers to fix their devices rather than dispose of them can significantly reduce e-waste and its directly effects on the environment and economy.

ii. Government Benefits of Expanding Right to Repair Legislation

Expanding Right to Repair legislation from state-level initiatives to comprehensive federal laws in the U.S could have substantial benefits for governments as well. According to U.S Public Interest Research group (PIRG) Opting for repairs instead of replacements can save households approximately \$330 each year, amounting to over \$40 billion nationwide. Consumers are increasingly inclined to embrace repair options, As public awareness of sustainability and the impact of e-waste grows, consumers are going to choose repair options, which could reduce the strain on governments efforts towards e-waste

management.

In addition, the Right to repair could stimulate job creation and market growth within repair sector. This shift would not only generate new employment opportunities but also foster educational programs focused on device repair, which will have a direct impact on the country's economy. According to a study published in Waste Advantage Magazine, the Right to Repair has the potential to reduce e-waste by up to 30%. This reduction would affect on waste management and lower the costs associated with recycling and managing e-waste. In practical terms, the annual e-waste generated in the U.S around 7 million tonnes, could decrease to 5 million tonnes with more strict legislations and increased repairability. This reduction would not only benefit consumers but also help governments manage e-waste more effectively and economically.

i. The Economic Impact of the Right to Repair on The Producers

For producers, the shift towards repairability presents new opportunities for revenue through the sale of spare parts and repair services. Producers might also need to adjust product pricing strategies to align with the enhanced focus on repairability.

The main challenge for producers will be the potential reduction in profits, as customers may opt to repair their devices rather than purchase new ones. This shift could affect their sales volumes. To address this issue, there are several suggestions can be considered:

1- Governments incentives and subsidies: Governments should provide incentives and subsidies to encourage producers to adopt the right to repair concept. Such support will motivate producers to help consumers to save money by offering more flexibility and options for device repairs.

2- Tax on Non-repairable Devices: Implementing a tax on non-repairable devices could be considered. Producers who do not comply the right to repair right standers should pay repair tax, in addition to the fine determined by laws. The revenue from this tax could then be used to support producers who adhere the right to repair principles, which will help to create a fair competitive environment and encourage compliance.

3- Revenue from spare parts purchasing: When considering the profits of these producers, it is important to recognize that the right to repair also includes the right to access spare parts, like I phone batteries, lap tops screens. This will open a new revenues stream for producers through the sale of spare parts, which can compensate for the potential reduction in profits from decreased sales of new devices.

In summary, implementing federal Right to Repair legislation supports consumer rights while offering significant economic and environmental benefits. It represents a crucial

step towards addressing the growing e-waste problem and fostering a more sustainable and economically viable system.

4. Right to repair laws

A. Right to Repair Laws in the United States

In the United States, there are currently four effective right to repair laws in New York, California, Colorado, Minnesota. Several other states are in the process of enacting similar laws, which could be a precursor to federal Right to Repair law.

In California, the right to repair Act (AB 244) was passed and effective on July 1, 2024. This legislation requires manufacturers of electronic and appliance product sold within the state, whether directly to consumers or through other channels, to provide parts, tools, and documentation necessary for the diagnosis, maintenances, or repair f these products to product owners, service facilities, and service dealers on fair and reasonable terms. Exemptions apply to certain categories like video game consoles, alarm system, and agricultural equipment. Through this legislation Californians will be able to get the parts, tools, and information needed to keep devices working longer and out of landfills, resulting in cost saving for Californians money and reduction the toxic electronic waste in environmental.[22]

The New York digital fair repair Act (DEFRA) (Gen. Bus. Law § 399-NN (2022), mandates that original equipment manufacturers (OEMs) to make diagnostic and repair information for digital electronic parts and equipment available to independent repair providers and consumers if such parts and repair information are also available to authorized repair providers. A significant drawback of this law is that it excludes any "product sold under a specific business-to-government or business-to-business contract ... not otherwise offered for sale directly by a retail seller," and now only applies to products made after July 1, 2023.[23] This exclusion restricts governments and companies, such as universities, schools, federal agencies, from practicing the right to repair, even though these entities should have a higher priority for this right, as they purchase large quantities of devices every year. They should be able to repair these devices to ensure longer usability. Furthermore, the restrictions limit the responsibilities of manufacturers to products after July 1, 2023, which could limit access to repair for devices sold prior. Ideally, consumers should have the right to repair for their devices sold since fixed years determined by experts.

The New York digital fair repair Act prohibits manufacturers from using parts pairing to prevent independent repair providers or owners from installing or enabling replacement parts, reduce the functionality or performance of digital electronic equipment, or cause misleading alerts or warnings about unidentified parts.

In 202, Colorado passed Right to Repair for Powered Wheelchairs, and expanded this right to include Farm Equipment in 2023. The law applies to devices manufactured or first sold in the state as of January 1, 2023 for Wheelchairs and January 1, 2024 for Farm Equipment. Notably, the Colorado law excludes Digital Electronic Equipment.[24]

Approved by Governor on May 28, 2024, the new act HB24-1121," Consumer Right to Repair Digital Electronic Equipment will be effective in Colorado on and January 1, 2026. The act expands the scope of the right-to-repair statutes to include digital electronic equipment manufactured and sold or used for the first time in Colorado on or after July 1, 2021.

Colorado has taken a significant step to extend the period of legal coverage to include products manufactured or sold after this date. This is a great step, and it is hoped that New York and other states will follow suit in extending their legal coverage periods.

This new act prohibits manufacturers from using parts pairing to prevent independent repair provider or owner from installing or enabling replacement parts, reduces the functionality or performance of the digital electronic equipment, or causes misleading alerts or warnings about unidentified parts.[25]

On July 1, 2024, Minnesota's New Digital Fair Repair Act Went into Effect. According to Minn. Stat. § 325E.72, the Digital Fair Repair Act requires manufactures of certain electronic products to make documentation, parts, and tools for diagnosis, maintenance, or repair available to independent repair providers and product owners on fair and reasonable terms.

Here is example of how this act works according to Minnesota general attorney official page: if Omar has a smartphone that needs a repair, he can choose to get his phone repaired by a repair provider authorized by the manufacturer of the phone, an independent repair provider, or himself. The manufacturer is required to make documentation, parts, and tools available to independent repair providers and Omar—not only the authorized repair provider.

It important to notice that this law does not apply for motor vehicles, medical devices, off-road equipment such as farm machinery and tractors, and video game consoles. Additionally, this act includes good standing, as enacted in Colorado, extends legal coverage to devices that were either manufactured or initially sold within the state starting from July 1, 2021, which provides consumers with greater protection.

B. EU Parliament Adopts 'Right to Repair' Directive: Key Impacts and Expectations

On April 16, 2024 EU Parliament adopted a significant directive known as “Right to Repair” (R2RD). This new law legislation aims to bolster the EU repair market and reduce repair costs for consumers. Under the directive, Manufacturers are required to provide spare parts and tools at a reasonable price and are prohibited from using contractual clauses, hardware or software techniques that hinder repairs.[26]

The directive mandates the manufacturer to repair common household products such as washing machines, vacuum cleaners, and smartphones, with a reasonable timeframe. If repair is not feasible, manufactures should offer consumers a refurbished products as attentive.[27] This directive is being implemented under Article 114 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union (TFEU).[28]

According to the European Commission, Consumers currently lose around €12 billion annually by replacing goods rather than repairing them. The European Commission anticipates that this new lawn will result in a reduction of around 18 million tonnes of CO2 over 15 years ann consumers will save €176 billion.[29]

E-Waste is a malignant disease, invading like serious attack, demanding significant effect efforts and corporate for all parties the governments, manufactures, and customers.

My real experience with Samsung Galaxy Note Edge underscores the urgent need for as comprehensive right to repair legislations. Faced with high repair cost and long wait times, coupled with indirect pressure to purchase a new device, the limitation of current repair options are so clear. This situation shows two important issues: the need for broader repair accessibility beyond the manufacturer and potential benefits of allowing third party repair shops to obtain and use parts. The right to repair is not merely matter of convenience, it is a main element in combating the growing of global e-waste crisis, in addition to, it contributes to mitigation climate by helping to reduce the greenhouse gas emissions.

The emotional connection we form with our devise, akin to the relationship depicted in “Toy Story,” highlights why we should value our possessions and seek extend their lifespan. The right to repair maintain this connection between past and future. The right to repair aligns with thus sentiment by enabling us to mend rather than discard our cherished items.

E-waste represents a significant environmental and economic challenge. The staggering statistics, including the projected increased increase in global e-waste and its low recycling rates with only recycling 17%, emphasizes the need for actional solutions starting from the roots. Implementing robust right-to-repair laws can mitigate e-waste by facilitating repairs, reducing the frequency of device replacement, and curbing greenhouse gas emissions associated with the manufacturing and disposal of electronics.

Furthermore, right-to-repair legislation offers substantial economic benefits by reducing consumer costs and fostering job creation within the repair industry. The evidence suggests that consumers, producers, and governments alike stand to gain from a shift towards repairability, making the case for broader legislative action compelling.

In summary, the right to repair is a vital element of a sustainable future, not only addressing the practical needs of consumers but also the broader issues of environmental degradation and economic inefficiency. As such, it is important that support and advocate for stronger right-to-repair laws to foster a more sustainable and equitable technological landscape.

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